

Shift of Dominant Eigenvalue in Curved Surface Nodal Method

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803845

ABSTRACT

The numerical solution of the steady-state neutron transport equation is primarily concerned with the dominant eigenvalue of the discrete system, which corresponds to the inverse of the effective multiplication factor. When the Curved Surface Nodal (CSN) method is applied to non-regular curved surface nodes, it has been observed that the dominant eigenvalue of the discrete system is shifted compared to the physical effective multiplication factor and the physical eigenvalue exists among all the eigenvalues but is not necessarily the largest one. This phenomenon is not observed with regular nodes. This paper investigates the effects of the expansion order, weight functions and the number of weighted residual equations associated boundary conditions. However, the shifting issue of the effective multiplication factor persists. The cause is believed to be the removal of higher-order weighted residual equations, which introduces systematic bias and causes the incomplete weighted residual approximation to overwhelm the physical dominant eigenvalue in problems with non-regular nodal discretization. To address this, a strategy combining all weighted residual equations has been implemented. Numerical results show that it is a feasible solution in tackling such dominant eigenvalue shifting issue.

Keywords: Neutron transport equation, Curved surface nodal method, Polynomial expansion, Weighted residual method, Eigenvalue problem

1. INTRODUCTION

Curved surface nodal (CSN) method is a novel numerical approach for solving neutron transport equation [1]. This method could solve neutron transport equation with curved surface nodes which are consistent with actual core geometry, thereby eliminating the piecewise linear approximation of curved structure. Consequently, CSN could maintain high computational accuracy while with relatively large curved surface nodes.

The essence of CSN method is to directly expand spatial dependence of nodal angular neutron flux using non-orthogonal multi-dimensional polynomials. The expansion coefficients are solved by the weighted residual method [2]. The essential idea is to minimize truncated-expansion induced residuals in neutron transport equation as well as boundary condition with respect to a certain weight function space, e.g. making the residual being orthogonal to the weight function space by keeping its corresponding residual component being vanished. These residual components are termed as weighted residual equations (WREs). In fact, many variants of polynomial expansion based weighted residual methods have been extensively studied and widely applied in solving neutron transport problem. These methods are different from each other in terms of strategies in organizing WREs, e.g. residuals from differential equations and boundary conditions, to form the linear system of expansion

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coefficients. The most representative methods are nodal expansion method (NEM) [3], variational nodal method (VNM) [4] and finite elements method (FEM) [5].

During the development of CSN method, one of the strategies in constructing linear system follows the idea in NEM method [6]. Specifically, within each curved surface nodal, 0th-order weighted residual equations (WREs) for the neutron transport equation and nodal boundary conditions are chosen to ensure neutron balance. The remaining higher order WREs for the neutron transport equation are then supplemented to ensure the linear system being well-defined, e.g. number of equations being equal with the number of unknowns.

However, it was discovered that this strategy led to non-convergence issue during source iterations when applied to curved surface nodes [7]. The underlying cause is identified as the dominant eigenvalue of the formed linear system exceeding the dominant eigenvalue of the underlying partial differential equation, which does not occur in rectangular nodes. There is no literature reported on the shifting issue of dominant eigenvalue in the discretized linear systems. This paper provides a detailed exposition of CSN method and utilizes a trivial model to investigate such numerical phenomenon. Further, a feasible solution is proposed to address the issue.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 recaps CSN method. Section 3 elucidates the shifting phenomenon of dominant eigenvalue with a homogeneous pin-cell model. By adjusting the choice of WREs in forming the linear system, its effect on linear system's dominant eigenvalue shifting is discussed and a feasible solution is proposed to avoid such shifting. Section 4 presents the conclusions.

2. METHODOLOGY OF CURVED SURFACE NODAL METHOD

2.1. Main Idea of CSN Method

Without loss of generality, the study and discussion focus on two-dimensional steady-state multi-group neutron transport equation shown as in Eq. (1).

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega_{xyi} \cdot \nabla \psi_{gi}(x, y) + \Sigma_{tg}(x, y) \psi_{gi}(x, y) &= S_{gi}(x, y), & (x, y) \in D \\ \psi_{gi}^{\text{in}}(x, y) &= \psi_{gi}^{\text{b}}(x, y), & (x, y) \in \partial D\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

where $\Omega_{xyi} = \sin \theta_i \cos \varphi_i \mathbf{x} + \sin \theta_i \sin \varphi_i \mathbf{y}$ is the discretized solid angle of neutrons and θ_i, φ_i are polar and azimuthal angle. \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} are unit vector along x-axis and y-axis, respectively. ψ is angular neutron flux, Σ_t is total macroscopic cross-section, S is combined scattering and fission source term. ψ^{b} is the boundary value for angular neutron flux on ∂D . Subscript g and i are indices for neutron energy group and discretized solid angle.

With energy and solid angle being discretized, Eq. (1) describes the spatial dependence of angular neutron flux $\psi_{gi}(x, y)$. For spatial variables, CSN method discretizes the solving domain into a number of curved surface nodes in a way that material in each node is kept uniform. Then, truncated multidimensional function series $P_k(x, y), k = 0, \dots, K_f - 1$ are employed to expand neutron angular flux $\psi_{gi}(x, y)$ within each node as in Eq. (2).

$$\psi_{gi}(x, y) \approx \sum_{k=0}^{K_f-1} P_k(x, y) \psi_{gik} \quad (2)$$

where $P_k(x, y), k = 0, \dots, K_f - 1$ is denoted as a set of basis functions which determine the capacity in expressing nodal angular neutron flux spatial distribution. ψ_{gik} is the expansion coefficient which represents the extent to which its corresponding basis function affects the shape of the distribution. These coefficients are spatially independent within each node, and take different values among nodes. Due to the arbitrariness of curved surface node in shape and size, it is challenging to prescribe suitable orthogonal polynomials. Therefore, a set of polynomial basis based on Taylor's expansion has been employed, such as in Eq. (3), where (\bar{x}, \bar{y}) is the coordinate of nodal geometric center.

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_0 &= 1, & P_1 &= x - \bar{x}, & P_2 &= y - \bar{y}, \\
 P_3 &= (x - \bar{x})^2/2, & P_4 &= (y - \bar{y})^2/2, & P_5 &= (x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y}), \dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The finite-order expansion introduces truncation errors, which prevent Eq. (1) from being strictly satisfied, resulting in residuals on both sides of the equation. The weighted residual method is employed to minimize the residual in a certain weight function space. Galerkin projection is used where the weight function space is spanned by $P_k(x, y), k = 0, \dots, K_f - 1$. The minimized residual is accomplished by multiplying with it a weight function $P_{k'}(x, y)$ and making its domain integration being zero. The k' -th order Galerkin weighted residual equation (WRE) is expressed as in Eq. (4).

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\sum_{k=0}^{K_f-1} \left[\psi_{gik} \iint_D P_{k'}(x, y) \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{xyi} \cdot \nabla P_k(x, y) dx dy \right] + \sum_{k=0}^{K_f-1} \left[\Sigma_{tg} \psi_{gik} \iint_D P_{k'}(x, y) P_k(x, y) dx dy \right] \\
 &= \iint_D P_{k'}(x, y) S_{gi}(x, y) dx dy, \quad k' = 0, 1, 2, \dots, K_f - 1 \\
 &\sum_{k=0}^{K_f-1} \left[\psi_{gik}^c \int_{\partial D \in c} \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{xyi} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\partial D} P_{k'}(x, y) P_k^c(x, y) ds - \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \psi_{gik}^n \int_{\partial D \in n} \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{xyi} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\partial D} P_{k'}(x, y) P_k^n(x, y) ds \right] = 0, \quad k' = 0, 1, 2, \dots, K_f - 1, \\
 &\hspace{10em} \text{continuity condition} \\
 &\sum_{k=0}^{K_f-1} \left[\psi_{gik} \int_{\partial D} \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{xyi} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\partial D} P_{k'}(x, y) P_k(x, y) ds - \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \beta \psi_{gi'k} \int_{\partial D} \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{xyi'} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\partial D} P_{k'}(x, y) P_k(x, y) ds \right] = 0, \quad k' = 0, 1, 2, \dots, K_f - 1, \\
 &\hspace{10em} \text{albedo boundary condition}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where c is the center node, n is its corresponding neighbor node. β is albedo and $\beta = 0$ is vacuum and $\beta = 1$ is reflective. i' is the reflective angle of solid angle i .

The neutron transport equation is now transformed into an algebraic equation set. For each discretized solid angle, energy group and node, the angular flux is expanded using K_f polynomials which presents K_f unknown expansion coefficients. However, in order to account for all the WREs derived from neutron transport equation and its boundary condition, there are $2K_f$ WREs which poses an over-determined problem. To address the issue of having more equations than unknowns, the strategy of discarding certain equations, similar to that in two-node NEM method, is adopted. The following section will provide a detailed exposition of the linear system construction schemes based on this approach.

2.2. Linear System in CSN

In CSN method, the scheme for selecting WREs is as follows: 0th-order WREs for neutron transport equation and the 0th-order WREs for the nodal boundary conditions are selected to guarantee neutron balance within each curved surface node. To ensure that the number of equations equals with the number of unknowns, remaining equations were then supplemented by other WREs for neutron transport equations. Table I presents the linear system construction schemes for first-order, second-order and third-order expansions under the assumption that each node has two boundary interfaces in average along with neutron direction. Taking an expansion order of 2 as an example, there are 6 expansion basis functions and 6 expansion coefficients. For each of the two incident boundary interfaces, introduce a WRE with a weight function of 1. For the neutron transport equation within node, to ensure neutron balance, a WRE with a weight function of 1 must also be introduced. The remaining 3 equations are then selected from the WREs of the neutron balance equations with weight functions of x , y , and xy , ensuring six equations for six unknowns.

Table I. Equation construction schemes.

Order of expansion	Basis functions	Weight functions at interfaces	Weight functions within node
1	$1, x - \bar{x}, y - \bar{y}$	1	1
2	$1, x - \bar{x}, y - \bar{y}, (x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y}),$ $(x - \bar{x})^2/2, (y - \bar{y})^2/2$	1	$1, x, y, xy$
3	$1, x - \bar{x}, y - \bar{y}, (x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y}),$ $(x - \bar{x})^2/2, (y - \bar{y})^2/2,$ $(x - \bar{x})^2(y - \bar{y})/2, (x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})^2/2,$ $(x - \bar{x})^3/3, (y - \bar{y})^3/3$	1	$1, x, y, xy,$ x^2, y^2, x^3, y^3

With chosen WREs being properly devised, a well-defined linear system for the expansion coefficient is conducted. By combining the equations across all energy groups and discrete solid angles and placing the scattering source term on the left-hand of the equation, a generalized eigenvalue problem is formulated as in Eq. (5).

$$(\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{S})\psi = \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}}\mathbf{F}\psi \quad (5)$$

where $1/k_{\text{eff}}$ should correspond to the largest eigenvalue of neutron transport equation [8].

For the linear generalized eigenvalue problem obtained after numerical discretization, as shown in Eq. (5), it can be transformed into a conventional eigenvalue problem as in Eq. (6). The largest eigenvalue and its corresponding eigenvector can then be obtained using eigenvalue decomposition of $(\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{S})^{-1}\mathbf{F}$. If the discrete system is a valid approximation of the original differential equation, then the largest eigenvalue obtained through eigenvalue decomposition should be the effective multiplication factor of the original differential equation that dominates the asymptotic behavior of physical system.

$$(\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{S})^{-1}\mathbf{F}\psi = k_{\text{eff}}\psi \quad (6)$$

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

To validate the proposed methods and investigate the numerical phenomena, a trivial model is employed. The model consists of a rectangular geometry with one-group uniform material properties. The boundary conditions are all reflective. The macroscopic cross-sections are shown in Table II.

Table II. Cross-sections of test model.

Σ_t/cm^{-1}	Σ_a/cm^{-1}	$\nu\Sigma_f/\text{cm}^{-1}$	Σ_s/cm^{-1}
1.0	0.6	0.6	0.4

This problem represents a two-dimensional homogeneous infinite slab, where the flux should be uniformly distributed regardless of the geometric dimensions. The effective multiplication factor k_{eff} is equal to multiplication factor in the infinite medium k_{inf} :

$$k_{\text{eff}} = k_{\text{inf}} = \frac{\nu\Sigma_f}{\Sigma_a} = 1.0 \quad (7)$$

CSN method discretizes this rectangular model into 12 curved surface nodes and rectangular nodes, as shown in Figure 1. Calculate the dominant eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{S})^{-1}\mathbf{F}$ under varying size of models, and their difference with the physical effective multiplication factor is shown in Figure 2, in which green

color indicates better agreement with physical eigenvalues, which is 1.0. In the case of curved surface nodes, nodal sizes are described with residual R and width of square L . R should be smaller than $L / 2$. L ranges from 1.0 cm to 5.0 cm, with increments of 0.1 cm; R ranges from 0.0 cm to 2.5 cm, with increments of 0.01 cm. In the case of rectangular nodes, nodal sizes are described with length L and width W , in which L ranges from 1.0 cm to 5.0 cm, with increments of 0.1 cm; W ranges from 0.0 cm to 2.5 cm, with increments of 0.01 cm. It can be observed that:

- (1) For curved surface nodes: The largest eigenvalue of the matrix $(\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{S})^{-1}\mathbf{F}$ does not always correspond to the physical effective multiplication factor. Further investigation indicates that the physical effective multiplication factor exists within the eigenvalue spectrum, however it is not the largest one.
- (2) For rectangular nodes: The scheme of discarding certain equations does not affect the agreement of the largest eigenvalue of $(\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{S})^{-1}\mathbf{F}$ with the physical effective multiplication factor for any nodal size.

Figure 1. Nodal discretization of trivial model.

(a) Consistency of dominant eigenvalues with curved surface nodal discretization

(b) Consistency of dominant eigenvalues with rectangular nodal discretization

Figure 2. Consistency of dominant eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{S})^{-1}\mathbf{F}$ under different sized nodal discretization with the second-order expansion (greener colors indicate better agreement with physical eigenvalues, which is 1.0).

To identify the underlying cause of the issue, three potential influencing factors have been identified:

- (1) Order of basis function expansion: This includes the first-order expansion with three basis functions, the second-order expansion with six basis functions, and the third-order expansion with ten basis functions.
- (2) Weight functions applied at boundaries: The weight functions applied at the boundaries are considered. Specifically, the integral average leakage constraint is equivalent to taking $P_{k'} = 1$. Modified these weight functions to: x and y , x^2 and y^2 , $x^2 + y^2$, and $x^2 + y^2 + 1$.
- (3) Number of residual equations of boundary conditions: This involves increasing the number of chosen WREs at nodal boundaries while correspondingly decreasing the number of WREs within the nodal subdomains. For example, in the second-order expansion, two WREs are applied to each incident surface; in the third-order expansion, three WREs are applied to each incident surface.

Table IV presents the results of the dominant eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{S})^{-1}\mathbf{F}$ for different computational schemes based on a model with an internal circle radius $R = 0.3$ cm and outer square box of lengths L being 1 cm, 2 cm, and 3 cm, respectively.

Table IV. Dominant eigenvalues for the curved surface nodal discretization under three specific nodal sizes

Influencing Factors	Schemes	$L = 1$ cm, $R = 0.3$ cm	$L = 2$ cm, $R = 0.3$ cm	$L = 3$ cm, $R = 0.3$ cm
Order of basis function expansion	1 st order	1.0	1.0	1.0
	2 nd order	1.1940	1.0	8.8987
	3 rd order	-51.6733	-3.9901	-9.8910
Weight functions applied at boundaries	x and y	1.1395	1.0	-5.0306
	x^2 and y^2	4.2363	1.0	-11.6672
	$x^2 + y^2$	1.0	1.0	1.8330
	$x^2 + y^2 + 1$	1.0584	1.0	-298.48
Number of WREs of incident surfaces	2 WREs per incident surface	-6.5236	1.0	1.0
	3 WREs per incident surface	$3.0529 \pm 1.9440i$	2.1111	$2.0025 \pm 0.6885i$

It can be observed that all the above factors influence the dominant eigenvalue, and they all exhibit a phenomenon of shift in the magnitude of the dominant eigenvalue, and the physical eigenvalue exists in the eigenvalue spectrum but is not necessarily the largest one. Other potential influencing factors such as nodal shape, presence of curved surfaces, and angular discretization were investigated, yielding consistent results.

Additionally, the dominant eigenvalue of the linear system is complex in some cases. In reactor physics, the k-eigenvalue problem seeks to determine the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} . Physically, this value must be real and positive. When approximating the spatial distribution of angular flux using a polynomial function space, numerical oscillations may occur in regions where the grid spacing is too coarse or the flux gradient is too steep. This can lead to locally negative flux values. Such negative flux disrupts the positivity of the system matrix, causing the eigenvalue spectrum to shift. Consequently, the original real principal eigenvalues may split into a pair of conjugate complex values.

The cause of this phenomenon, after investigation, is believed to be the removal of higher-order weighted residual equations, particularly those at the boundaries, which introduces systematic bias. In problems with non-regular nodal discretization, the incomplete weighted residual approximation causes the physical dominant eigenvalue shift. Inspired by [9], a strategy of combining WREs has been implemented. Specifically, for the WREs of the control equations and boundary conditions as in Eq. (8), where R_c is the residual of control equations and R_B is the residual of boundary conditions.

$$\begin{aligned} \iint_D P_{k'} R_C dx dy &= 0, & k' &= 0, 1, 2, \dots, K_f - 1 \\ \iint_{\partial D} P_{k'} R_B dx dy &= 0, & k' &= 0, 1, 2, \dots, K_f - 1 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Combine two Weighted Residual Equations (WREs) with the same weight functions to form a composite residual equation:

$$\iint_D P_{k'} R_C dx dy - \sum_{s=1}^{N_s} \iint_{\partial D_s} P_{k'} R_B dx dy = 0, \quad k' = 0, 1, 2, \dots, K_f - 1 \quad (9)$$

This approach ensures that all WREs for the control equations and boundary conditions under all weight functions can be utilized, thereby avoiding the discarding of any equations. The results recalculated for different curved surface nodal sizes of second-order expansion based on this scheme are shown in Figure 3. It can be observed that this scheme effectively addresses the issue of the shift in the dominant eigenvalue of the linear system.

Figure 3. Consistency of dominant eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{S})^{-1}\mathbf{F}$ at different nodal sizes under the second-order expansion by combining residual equations scheme (greener colors indicate better agreement with physical eigenvalues, which is 1.0).

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper reports the application of the Curved Surface Nodal (CSN) method to curved surface non-regular nodes. The CSN method employs a scheme for selecting certain WREs initially. It was found that a discrepancy occurs between the dominant eigenvalue of the discretized linear system and the physical effective multiplication factor, and the physical eigenvalue exists among all the eigenvalues but is not necessarily the largest one.

Three potential influencing factors were investigated, including the order of basis function expansion, the weight functions applied at the boundaries, and the number of residual equations for the boundary conditions. However, the issue of dominant eigenvalue shift persists.

The underlying cause was found to be the removal of higher-order weighted residual equations, particularly at the boundaries. In problems involving non-regular nodal discretization, the incomplete weighted residual approximation causes the physical dominant eigenvalue shift. To address this issue, a scheme for combining residual equations was proposed and implemented. From the numerical results, it is found to be a feasible solution to tackle such shifting issue of dominant eigenvalue.

Future work will delve into the differences among these two schemes, attempting to analyze the causes of the observed phenomena and the strengths and weaknesses of each approach from a theoretical standpoint. Additionally, analyses of convergence and computational stability will be conducted.

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